

ISic0408

Monumental Latin fragment

Language

Latin

Type

uncertain

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.09.10

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

contrada Bufardecì,

Coordinates

37.0673281, 15.2804126

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 253

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---][][---]
2. [tr]ibuno · [---]
3. [p]raef[---]

Apparatus

Preliminary text based on autopsy

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491619

EDCS 21900450

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7128 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Schubring, J. 1865. Über das neu ausgegrabene römische Gebäude in der campagna Bufardecì zu Syrakus. *Monatsberichte der königlichen preussischen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Berlin*. 362-372. At 372 no.1

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Photo J. Prag